

INT'L COOPERATION

- Projects
- Partnerships
- Joint Research Units
- International Positions
- Achievements

Projects

International Cooperative Projects

Area of Cooperation	Cooperative Institution/Country
Diagnosis of Congenital CMV Infections in Newborn Infants	University of Alabama, the United States
Combating the Next SARS- or MERS-like Emerging Infectious Disease Outbreak by Improving Active Surveillance	Duke-NUS Graduate Medical School Singapore, Singapore
Studies on Biological Control of Vector Transmitting Diseases Collaboration	Biological Research Center, Defense Science and Technology Organization, Pakistan
Geographical Distribution and Genetic Variation of the Pathogens in Africa	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya
Emerging Infectious Diseases along the "Belt and Road"	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya
Study and Construction of Biosafety Strategic Consulting Think-Tank	University of North Texas, the United States
Viruses and Genetic Resource Database	EcoHealth Alliance, the United States
Targeting CpxR signalling for antibacterial therapy	Ume University, Sweden
Fc engineering for increasing its biological properties implying for development of Fc-based therapeutics	Novo Nordisk Research Centre, Denmark
European Virus goes global	European Union, Université d'Aix-Marseille, France
Mutual interaction of chronic viruses with cells of the immune system: from fundamental research to immunotherapy and vaccination	University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Research of Major Antigenic Proteins of Influenza Virus	Harvard University, the United States
The Study on the Mechanism of Drug-resistant HIV Prevalent Strains Formation in Mid-west Region in China	National Institute of Infectious Diseases, Japan
Cytomegalovirus Gene Function in Virulence and Replication	The National Institutes of Health, the United States
Prevention and Control of Pathogenic Microorganism and Epidemics in Africa	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya
Study on Enterovirus 71 (EV71)	Institution Novartis, Singapore
Resistance of Influenza Virus in Environmental Reservoirs and Systems	Institut Pasteur, France
Innate Immunity in Influenza Virus Infection of Mammalian Airways	FP6, European Union

The Epidemic Disease Detection Project of the Domestication and Breeding of Wild Geese and Ducks in Poyang Lake	Food and Agriculture Organization, UN
Portable Biosensors Based on Lab-on-a-chip Technology for Environmental Pollution Monitoring	University of Southampton, the United Kingdom
Emerging Pandemic Threats PREDICT	National Wildlife Federation, the United States
Purification of Expressed Protein of Baculovirus	Department of Molecular and Cell Biology, Campus Univ, Spain
HIV Transmission and Prevention	St George's University of London, Britain
Baculovirus-Insect Host Cell Interactions	Wagenigen Agriculture University, Netherlands
Key technologies for the construction of high-level bio-safety laboratory and for emerging infectious disease control	Lyon P4 Laboratory, France
Construction of the System of Standards for Biosafety Management of the Biosafety Laboratories	AFSSAPS, AFNOR, Lyon P4 Laboratory, INSERM Jean Merieux, France
Avian Influenza Surveillance of Migratory Birds in Southern China	International Development Research Center, Canada
The Transfer of nucleocapsid of Baculovirus in Insect Cell and Mammalian Cell	Wagenigen Agriculture University, Netherlands

Achievements

No.	Paper Information
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